

Slovak Archive of Social Data (SASD)

as a national service provider for CESSDA ERIC

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EOSC Slovak National Tripartite Event, Slovak Centre of Scientific and
Technical Information (CVTI SR), Lamačská cesta 8A, 840 05 Bratislava, Slovakia

Date: 31 May 2023, 09:30-14:00

Mission since 2004

- Provide open access to (not only) publicly-funded social science (survey) research data
- Enhance secondary analysis of available data
- Standardize and improve methodology of empirical research in social sciences

2004 Slovak Archive of Social Data (SASD) established within a national project

2013 April 12

together with Portugal, Slovakia became the last „old“ CESSDA member at the last meeting of CESSDA in Budapest

December 16

The Minister of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic signed a letter indicating the willingness of Slovakia to join CESSDA as an observer

2014 June 12

Slovakia became observer in CESSDA AS

2017 March 24

Request for the setting-up of CESSDA ERIC from Slovakia

- June 2017 – Slovakia became a founding member of CESSDA-ERIC with SASD as the **National service provider for the Consortium of the European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA)**
- Currently, membership fees are covered by the Ministry of Education, operational costs are covered by the Institute for Sociology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences
- Available at: <http://sasd.sav.sk>

Number of datasets in SASD

Number of downloads from SASD

- INTRODUCTION ▶
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Search the archive

Look in the [data catalogue](#) or try the [advanced search](#).

Data Search catalogue

- [How Are You, Slovakia?, March 2021](#)** [SASD 2021002]
[Display found occurrences.](#) Found: 20
- [Values and society during the Covid-19 pandemic](#)** [SASD 2020007]
[Display found occurrences.](#) Found: 2
- [How Are You, Slovakia?, May 2020](#)** [SASD 2020003]
[Display found occurrences.](#) Found: 2
- [How Are You, Slovakia?, December 2020](#)** [SASD 2020006]
[Display found occurrences.](#) Found: 2
- [How Are You, Slovakia?, February / March 2022](#)** [SASD 2022001]
[Display found occurrences.](#) Found: 6
- [How Are You, Slovakia?, April 2020](#)** [SASD 2020002]
[Display found occurrences.](#) Found: 2
- [How Are You, Slovakia?, October / November 2020](#)** [SASD 2020005]
[Display found occurrences.](#) Found: 2
- [How Are You, Slovakia?, January / February 2021](#)** [SASD 2021001]
[Display found occurrences.](#) Found: 15
- [How Are You, Slovakia?, December 2021](#)** [SASD 2021006]
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- [How Are You, Slovakia?, May 2021](#)** [SASD 2021003]
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- [How Are You, Slovakia?, October 2021](#)** [SASD 2021005]
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- [How Are You, Slovakia?, July 2021](#)** [SASD 2021004]
[Display found occurrences.](#) Found: 17
- [How Are You, Slovakia?, September 2020](#)** [SASD 2020004]
[Display found occurrences.](#) Found: 3

Hint: Not enough results? Enter only a part of the string.
(Example: religious, religio, relig, ...)

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Data Data catalogue

How Are You, Slovakia?, April 2020

[study description](#) | [list of variables](#) | [data access](#)

Details for variable Q22

Name: Q22

Variable label: Ak by dnes bola dostupná vakcína na nový koronavírus, dali by ste sa zaočkovať?

Literal question:

Ak by dnes bola dostupná vakcína na nový koronavírus, dali by ste sa zaočkovať?

Label	Value		Frequency*	%*
áno	1		409	40.9
nie	2		278	27.8
neviem	3		313	31.3

Summary statistics

Total Responses:

Valid: 1000

Min. / max. value: 0 /

Mean / standard deviation: /

[\[previous variable \]](#) | [\[next variable \]](#)

[\[back \]](#)

***Caution:** Frequencies and percentages are calculated from unweighted data. If data were not collected using quota sampling, there could be significant differences between those unweighted values and the representative weighted figures.

Partnerships

- Cooperation with „Národné osvetové centrum“ [National centre of culture] at the Ministry of Culture, 20 data sets from 2020 – 2017 available via SASD
- Agreement with „Odbor koordinácie protidrogovej stratégie a monitorovania drog“ [Section of coordination of anti-drug strategy and drug monitoring]
- Aim is to become THE archive for (not only) publicly-funded survey data

A close-up, slightly blurred photograph of a computer keyboard. The keys are a light beige or cream color, and the letters are printed in a dark, sans-serif font. The lighting is warm and golden-yellow, creating a soft, glowing effect across the entire scene. The focus is on the central text, with the keyboard keys in the foreground and background being out of focus.

Thank you for your attention.

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sasd.sav.sk